

CLINICAL AND PSYCHOSOCIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MEN WITH ERECTILE DYSFUNCTION

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Relevance. In contrast to the impressive advances made in somatic research of erectile dysfunction (ED), psychogenic ED is mostly treated as a monolithic block or is merely defined by exclusion of organic factors. Erectile dysfunction (ED) is associated with psychological impairment, and further research is required to understand their relationship.

Methods

Patients completed clinical and health-related quality-of-life information at baseline and three follow-up points over 12 months; 162 patients had usable baseline data, including clinical history and current status, sociodemographic information, and standard paper-and-pencil scales of psychosocial characteristics. Scores on the International Index of Erectile Functioning erectile functioning subscale were collapsed into mild (N = 27), moderate (N = 41), or severe (N = 94) categories.

Results

Severe ED was significantly associated with not having a regular sex partner; a history of prostate cancer; and worse scores on measures of positive affect, belonging/loneliness, sexual self-efficacy-strength, psychological adjustment, marital happiness, anxiety at last intercourse, and depression. In a multivariate logistic regression model, poorer sexual self-efficacy was most closely associated with severe ED. The model rescaled R^2 was 0.63 (area-under-the-curve, 0.91).

Conclusions

Severe ED is related to impairment across a broad range of psychosocial domains, and clinicians should consider offering patients assistance in dealing with its psychosocial impact.

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